

NOW *THAT* IS REFLECTION

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PUBLISHED ON EDUBLOGS ON OCT 3, 2025

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17259270

We expect reflection from our students, but how often do we engage with reflection ourselves as educators?

Every once in a while the opportunity to immerse in reflection, away from the day-to-day, arrives. This week I was so pleased to rejoin my “LOL-buddies”, my cohort in the UU Educational Leadership Program, for a study visit to the University of Edinburgh. A place that is similar in many ways to Utrecht University- very big, with some 30,000 undergraduate students and broad, with nearly any discipline you can imagine represented in the study and research programs. And with an [Institute for Academic Development](#) supporting educational development, including professional development of educators, in a system that is very similar to the [UU Centre for Academic Teaching and Learning](#).

So perhaps unsurprisingly, we found ourselves facing many of the same challenges. How to engage with students at a personal level, and encourage such personal activities as reflection, in cohorts of hundreds of students? How do we do these things without continuously reinventing the wheel or simply stating the obvious? And how do we do these in times of financial uncertainty, which is even more at the foreground in the UK (though I fear this foreshadows where we are headed in the Netherlands).

I take away from this study trip a much deeper understanding of topics like co-creation and interdisciplinary education thanks to the wealth of knowledge present in Edinburgh, including which questions to ask. Catherine Boville’s discussion of her study on co-creation of curriculum, and

specifically asking students “what do you think a curriculum is?” was eye-opening. How do we expect students and educators to think about curricular co-design if their ideas are very different from ours on what that entails (Bovill & Woolmer, 2019)? What are we asking students to do when we ask them to co-create a curriculum- is that only content?

The transformative aspect for educators who engage in co-creation is another fascinating new aspect for me: the idea that “once I have developed education in co-creation, I would never go back” (I think this will be a this forthcoming publication by (Iii et al., 2025) - but am not sure I noted that right). I wonder about that; personally I feel this differently. I know that reciprocal engagement of societal partners in education is important and a highly effective way to teach, but it is also hard work. One of my take-homes for this week (along with a very long reading list) is that the same holds for co-creation of education with students: it is a highly effective means of reaching students in a very different way, but to do it well is also hard work.

If I’m brutally honest with myself, though vastly I prefer including students and societal partners, although obviously I would prefer to have the best possible education all the time, when under heavy time pressure, I probably would resort to “traditional” teaching. It feels intuitively better to do less effective methods well than highly effective methods badly. As the educator, I do feel a final responsibility in these collaborations, and don’t want to expose students or societal partners to poorly organized or poorly thought through experiences.

In all of this learning, there was also time to wander Edinburgh a bit, including the well worthwhile [National Museum of Scotland](#). In all of the reflection on reflection (and this was indeed another topic), bouncing ideas around with my LOL-buddies and my newly found educational colleagues in Edinburgh was the most transformative part of the trip. At the end of the trip a colleague and I stood in front of the enormous lighthouse lamp, complete with cut glass to send the light in all directions, and declared: “Now *that* is reflection!” Indeed, and sometimes making “light” (I know terrible pun) of the situation with colleagues, is the best reflection of all.

Bovill, C., & Woolmer, C. (2019). How conceptualisations of curriculum in higher education influence student-staff co-creation in and of the curriculum. *Higher Education*, 78(3), 407–422.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-018-0349-8>

Iii, G. D., Bovill, C., & Lundmark, A. M. (2025). The same but different: Teacher and student experiences of partnership. *Student Engagement in Higher Education Journal*.

<https://www.research.ed.ac.uk/en/publications/the-same-but-different-teacher-and-student-experiences-of-partner>